

Organizational Performance Of Moroccan Professional Football Academies: From Scoping Review To New Research Directions.

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Abstract:

The present article offers a scoping review approach developed by Arksey and O'Malley, to investigate the concept of organizational performance in sports industry, especially in the area of youth professional football academies. The review conducted a scoping review, leading to rigorous analysis of more than 50 studies exploring organizational effectiveness and performance management in football training centres. In this study, we utilized both Arksey and O'Malley's framework and PRISMA protocol for transparency and rigor, this scoping study maps the current state of knowledge and highlights significant theoretical and empirical gaps in the field. Indeed, the findings reveal that research remains on player development is predominantly, with limited consideration given to broader organizational issues such as governance, strategic management, human resources development, and stakeholder relations. Following this, this study makes a significant contribution by outlining a clear future research agenda organized into three main pillars: the construction of tailored multidimensional performance frameworks suitable for the Moroccan environment, the examination of institutional and cultural drivers of academy success, and the analysis of strategic management practices on sustainable talent development.

Keywords:

Organizational performance, sport, sport organizations, scoping review, systematic review

Introduction

The article presents a scoping review of organizational performance in sport industry. As such, the objective of conducting a scoping review is to generate a summary of the available relevant literature in sport management. Thus, scoping review differ from narrative and systematic review in the sense that the scoping review cover subject areas that encompass diverse kinds of studies and focusing on “mapping” a research field rather than resolving, narrowly defined research questions (Arksey and O’Malley, 2005). Beyond this, this research literature leads to many important gaps in the literature review and empirical in the studying the organizational performance in sport organizations.

In general, it is very difficult to figure out, explain and determine the context of organizational performance in sport clubs. In this sense, our article occurs in four phases. Firstly, we attempt to outline the theoretical framework of organizational performance. In the same way, an existing research of the relation between organizational performance and football industry in an organizational context. Then, we shall introduce the analytical approach adopted in this scoping review, namely the core research questions of our methodological study, search strategy and selection criteria used to search and select articles. In conclusion, we will examine these findings and outline directions for future research on organizational performance in sports. In this regard, this discussion will also identify critical gaps in the current literature between academic theory and real-world application in sports organizations.

In most cases, organizational performance is commonly conceptualized as the union of effectiveness and efficiency (Madella, Bayle & Tome, 2005; Mouzas, 2006). Effectiveness concerns how successfully organizations have achieved their results. On the other hand, efficiency understood as the relationship between the resources of an organization in relation to the outcomes obtained. These two concepts, efficiency and effectiveness are fundamental in outlining the theoretical framework of organizational performance. There is broad agreement in the literature that the concept of organizational performance signifies a complex and multidimensional construct (Kaplan, 2001; Shilbury & Moore, 2006). In general, performance is usually understood as the combination of efficiency, which demonstrated the relationship between inputs (resources used) and the produced outputs of the system (Madella, Bayle, &

Tome, 2005). And effectiveness, which is referred the ability to attain the institution's goals (Bayle & Madella, 2002).

Table 1. Example of Organizational Performance Definitions

Author	Definition
Madella et al. (2005)	<i>“The ability to acquire and process properly human, financial and physical resources to achieve the goals of the organization”</i>
Tayşir & Tayşir (2012)	<i>“The ability to achieve goals and implement strategies while using resources in a socially responsible manner”</i>
Winand et al. (2014)	<i>“The acquisition of necessary resources and their efficient use through the organization processes to achieve relevant and targeted goals, as well as a high satisfaction of the organization stakeholders”</i>

Source: auteurs

Moreover, it has been reported by researchers Baruch and Ramalho (2006), Kaplan (2001), Speckbacher (2003), and Stone et al., (1999), state that the definition of organizational performance for nonprofit organizations settings tends to be quite complex. Indeed, the concept of organizational performance has different meanings depending on the individual, the context and there are theoretical ambiguities and difficulties to define the concept and the process of evaluating it (Cameron, 1986; Quinn and Rohrbaugh, 1983). Nevertheless, in the sport management literature leads us to adopt the definition of organizational effectiveness suggested by Madella et al. (2005). It refers to the capacity to appropriately acquire and process human, financial and physical resources for the achievement of the organizational goals (Madella et al., 2005). Thus, organizational performance ought to be defined as the integration of the « *means and ends.* » in organizations. The “means” include various determinants of performance, including the human and managerial capabilities. The “ends”, on the other hand, correspond to the organization's strategic goals that serve as the fundamental reason of the organization's existence.

1. METHODS

The current study was performed from December 2024 to June 2025 (and was further updated on 19 May 2026) following a scoping approach. Indeed, this scoping review can be useful of the mapping the available evidence related a specific issue, recording trends and explaining core ideas (Munn et al., 2018). Furthermore, a scoping review is an approach to synthesizing research findings that focuses on exploratory research questions by searching key concepts, identifying different types of evidence, synthesizing existing literature and identifying gaps in the literature concerning a particular discipline or field of study (Colquhoun et al. 2014; Munn et al. 2018).

In the following review, we follow the methodological approach developed by Arksey and O'Malley (2005), which represents commonly acknowledged standards for scoping reviews and has been successfully applied by previous research in the areas of organizational perspectives and sport industry. This scoping review was conducted according to six steps, namely, **(1)** determining the research questions for investigation; **(2)** finding all pertinent studies on the topic; **(3)** study selection of relevant contributions; **(4)** mapping the data and **(5)** gathering, abstracting and documenting the findings. Furthermore, the review was conducted following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) Extension for Systematic Scoping. To summarize, our scoping of the literature started in December 2024 and needed approximately six months of work. The extended timeframe reflects the comprehensive nature of the work, which required multiple rounds of study identification, selection, and synthesis.

Figure 1. The protocol utilized in conducting the current study

Source: adapted from PRISMA protocol

1.1.IDENTIFICATION OF RESEARCH QUESTION

Indeed, Arksey and O'Malley (2005) contended that the research questions should guide the search strategy. Arguably, the research questions were developed to limit the comprehensive analysis through excessive process in order to capture relevant literature. As such, in line with the aims of our study, we developed four research questions to structure our work: **(1)** How is organizational performance defined in sport-related literature in the context of sports and football academies in particular? **(2)** How professional football academies attained organizational performance? **(3)** How is effectiveness perceived in football academies? And **(4)** what gaps and future research paths exist in the context of football academies and organizational performance?

Nonetheless, the categories listed below emerged from the conceptual discussion on organizational performance in the context of football youth academies and sport, presented in the second part of this paper. Likewise, these categories were subsequently refined by a thorough analysing of the relevant theoretical frameworks lining organizational effectiveness with sporting contexts:

1. The theoretical conceptualization of organizational performance ;
2. Study design and empirical research methodologies ;
3. Context (the object of organizational performance) and units of analysis ;
4. The relationship among organizational performance and football ;
5. Main themes identified across the articles.

1.2.DETERMINATION OF RELEVANT STUDIES

To find studies pertinent concerning the research question, the identification process was structured across two consecutive phases. In the first phase, we selected a relevant databases ('where to search') while the second phase focused on developing an appropriate search terms for querying these databases ('how to search'). More precisely, in order to respond to the central research inquiry, a range of multidisciplinary and topically relevant databases were located and then selected, and multiple search combinations were piloted and tested using the following

databases: Web of Science, Scopus and ScienceDirect, were systematically used to generate comprehensive results. Ultimately, a final search string was adopted:

(((((ALL=(organizational performance)) OR ALL=(organizational performance)) OR ALL=(organizational effectiveness)) OR ALL=(performance)) AND ALL=(sport organization)) OR ALL=(sport club)) OR ALL=(football club)) AND ALL=(football)) OR ALL=(football performance)) OR ALL=(soccer performance)) OR ALL=(professional football))

((ALL=(organizational performance)) OR ALL=(organizational effectiveness)) AND ((ALL=(football)) OR ALL=(football performance)) designed to optimally balance the breadth of results, their relevance, and the practical feasibility of the search. In particular, due to the common interchangeable use of the terms “effectiveness” and “performance” in the sport field, both were included in the search strategy to maximize the breadth in the search results. Otherwise, the terms “football academies” and “football clubs” were used as key search terms to align with the broad conceptualizations and definitions of sport adopted in this scoping review. Up until now, however, to ensure quality and relevance, the searches were limited to peer-reviewed journal publications and review articles published in English, French and Spanish published since 2015. Furthermore, the search strategy and inclusion criteria provided in Tables 5.

Table 2. Overview of search terms and databases

Boolean search terms	("organizational performance" OR "organizational effectiveness" OR "performance") AND ("sport organization" OR "sport club" OR "football club") AND ("football" OR "football performance" OR "soccer performance" OR "professional football")
Search area	Searches were conducted as follows: Web of Science: Topic field (Title, Abstract, Keywords, and Keyword Plus). Scopus: Title and Abstract fields.
Databases	Scopus; Web of Science / Web of Science Core Collection; ScienceDirect.

Source: authors

Beyond this, the query was confined in Scopus to the following subject areas: Business, Social Sciences, Management and Accounting. Since then, organizational research in sport field has shown an increasing attention to the concept of organizational performance, within the context of football, where both professional football clubs and youth academies face unique performance and development challenges. Currently, this study is undertaken with the aim of determining how broadly the concept of effectiveness has been expanded to domains other than football clubs and football academies.

1.2.1. DATABASES SELECTION

Across these studies, the central concern is identifying relevant databases resulted in the selection of three multidisciplinary databases: Scopus, Web of Science, and ScienceDirect. Similarly, these platforms were chosen because they are multidisciplinary databases that cover numerous research fields and topics, and their affiliation with different publishers.

1.2.2. SEARCH QUERY DEVELOPMENT

Additionally, the queries applied to the databases utilized a Boolean logic approach, linking multiple keywords using bool operators. The research questions guided the identification of four search components: **(1)** organizational effectiveness and sport organizations, **(2)** organizational performance and youth football academies, and **(3)** talent identification and development.

Table 3. Search components

Search components	Search Items (English)	Search Items (French)	Search Items (Spanish)
Search component 1: organizational effectiveness and sport organizations	“Organizational effectiveness”, “sport organizations”.	“Efficacité organisationnelle”, “organisations sportives”.	“Eficacia organizacional”, “organizaciones deportivas”.
Search component 2: Organizational	“Organizational performance”, “youth	“Performance organisationnelle”,	“Rendimiento organizacional”,

performance and youth football academies	football academies”, “soccer academies”, “professional football clubs”.	“académies de football”, “académies de football”, “centres de formation”, “clubs de football professionnel”.	“academias de fútbol”, “canteras de fútbol”, “clubes de fútbol profesionales”.
Search component 3: Talent identification and Development	“Talent identification”, “TID”, “talent development”, “TDE”, “scouting”.	“ Identification des talents ”, “développement des talents”, “détection”.	“Identificación de talentos”, “desarrollo de talentos”, “detección”.

Source: authors

Finally, the search terms were ultimately converted into structured queries for each target database. In this regard, the full queries are shown in table 3 and 4, respectively. In total, the search queries generated 13,164 records, which were subsequently reviewed and analyzed.

Table 4. Search queries

Database	Query
Scopus	"Organizational performance" OR "organisational performance" OR "organizational effectiveness" OR "organizational efficiency" OR "academy effectiveness" OR "academy performance" AND "sport organizations" OR "football clubs" OR "professional football clubs" OR "football training centre" OR "football academy" OR "football academies" OR "professional soccer academies" OR "youth soccer academy"
Web of Science	TITLE-ABS-KEY((performance OR effectiveness OR "organizational performance" OR "organizational effectiveness" OR "academy effectiveness" OR "professional soccer performance" OR "academy performance" OR "organizational productivity" OR "performance indicator") AND (football

	OR soccer OR "professional football" OR "professional soccer" OR "professional elite football" OR "youth soccer" OR "youth football" OR "football club academy") AND ("sports organizations" OR "professional sport clubs" OR "sports associations" OR "football associations" OR "sport club" OR "soccer academy" OR "football academy" OR "football academies" OR "football training centre" OR "academy soccer players" OR "professional soccer academies" OR "youth soccer academy"))
ScienceDirect	"Organizational performance" OR "organisational performance" OR "organizational effectiveness" OR "organizational efficiency" OR "academy effectiveness" OR "academy performance" AND "sport organizations" OR "football clubs"

Source: authors

1.3.STUDY SELECTION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA

The study analyzes articles related to organizational effectiveness of sport organizations, more specifically, professional football youth academies. For instance, the table 5 presents inclusion and exclusion criteria. From the first search, yielded access to n= 13,164 abstracts that were reviewed using an Excel sheet. We initially identified and removed 814 duplicated abstracts. Therefore, the next phase involved reviewing the remaining 12,350 abstracts looking in search of relevant studies focusing on football and organizational effectiveness.

Most studies were removed at this point according the following exclusion conditions:

- Studies that did not concentrate on the organizational aspects in football industry;
- Articles that conducted global analysis without exploring organizational performance in football settings;
- Articles focusing on professional football outside the scope of organizational effectiveness were excluded, because this perspective fell outside the defined boundaries of professional football clubs and youth academies, and
- A significant of the investigated articles was excluded since they did not address on effectiveness and sports organizations performance from an organizational perspective.

Table 5. Summary of inclusion/exclusion criteria

Study characteristics	Criteria	
	Inclusion	Exclusion
Topic	Text concerning the authors	
Population/Target group	Target groups of all ages and backgrounds.	None.
Design	Empirical studies using quantitative and/or qualitative methods	Meta-analysis, Systematic Reviews
Publication type	Full-length articles, Peer-reviewed journal articles	Book chapters, Grey literature
Languages	English, French and Spanish	Documents not in English
Geographic scope	Worldwide	None
Timeframe	2015 - 2026	Documents outside of defined range.
Period of literary research	December 2024 until June 2025	None.

Source: authors

The number of full-text articles assessed for eligibility reached thirty-three ($n = 33$). During this phase, nineteen articles ($n = 19$) were excluded. Moreover, it has been reported that, a more thorough analysis of the full texts revealed that they aligned with exclusion criteria mentioned above. In other cases, although the abstract included the term of organizational effectiveness, yet the concept was operationalized, empirically researched or even discussed in the full text. Thus, a total of one thirty-three articles ($n = 33$) articles were considered eligible for qualitative analysis. The following flowchart, adapted from PRISMA, which illustrates the entire search and selection process (Fig. 1 & 2).

Table 6. List of journals referenced within the literature search

Journals identified and screened	
European Sport Management Quarterly	Managing Sport and Leisure
International Journal of Sports Physiology and Performance	European Management Review
Journal of Sports Economics	Managing Leisure
Sport & Society	European Journal of Sport Science
International Journal of Performance Analysis in Sport	Journal of Sports Sciences
Journal of Sport Management	Sport Management Review
European Journal of Sport Science	Journal of Global Sport Management

Source: authors

1.4.CHARTING THE DATA AND COLLATING, ANALYZING, SUMMARIZING AND REPORTING RESULTS

Based on Arksey and O'Malley framework and existing scoping reviews conducted in the sport management field Inoue et al., (2015), this study utilized two categories of analytical methods: frequency analysis and qualitative thematic analysis. Indeed, an analysis of frequencies used as a descriptive statistical approach allowed to shows the number of occurrences for each variable including year of publication, geographic origin, journal title, methodological approach, and study population as key variables. In the other sense, the thematic analysis was engaged the first and second authors in this process, who systematically identified patterns across dataset in response to the proposed research questions. In the next phase, we carried out the extracting and charting data from the included studies. This operation was performed using Excel, during which we captured bibliographic, research design characteristics, methodological, programmatic and definitional information from every study that met the inclusion criteria. Additionally, in terms of bibliographic and methodological data, we extracted information included: authors, their affiliation, publication year, journal title; study country; study design; study duration, methodological approach, sample size, and the theoretical framework adopted.

Figure 2. PRISMA Flow Chart: Study identification, screening, and inclusion for the Scoping Review

Source: Adapted from Tricco et al. (2018).

2. FINDINGS

2.1.FREQUENCY ANALYSIS FINDINGS

Following full-text screening, 52 articles examining the topic of organizational performance on sport context based on the definitions and inclusion criteria presented above. In this sense, the final sample incorporated forty-four empirical studies, which comprised cross-sectional (n = 20), longitudinal (n = 2), intervention (n = 1), and case study designs (n = 2). These studies consisted of qualitative (n = 1), quantitative (n = 15), and mixed-methods (n = 4) research. A range of methodological tools applied across the studies (see Table 8) included such as semi-structured interviews and questionnaires being the most common.

Table 7. Study Descriptive Characteristics (Organizational performance; N=33)

Study Type	n	Studies
Literature Analysis	7	Williams et al. (2020); Raya-Castellano & Fradua (2015); Sharma & Singh (2019); Richard et al. (2009); Winand et al. (2014); Eydi et al. (2011); Barth et al. (2018).
Observational study	1	Kelly et al. (2020).
Case study	1	Bayle & Robinson (2007).
Surveying instrument	15	Frisby (1986); Chelladurai et al. (1987); Chelladurai & Haggerty (1991); Papadimitriou & Taylor (2000); Madella et al. (2005); Shilbury & Moore (2006); Papadimitriou (2007); Winand et al. (2010); Eydi (2013); Eydi et al. (2013); Nowy et al. (2015); Karteroliotis & Papadimitriou (2004); Wolfe et al. (2002).
Experimental study	1	Millar & Stevens (2012).
Interview study	4	Relvas et al. (2010); Mason et al. (2026); Koh-Tan (2011); Papadimitriou (1998).
Other	4	Jamil et al. (2021); Hamann & Schiemann (2021); Winand et al. (2011/2013); De Cock et al. (2025/2026).
n	33	

Source: authors

The following table provides an overview of the primary studies included in this review. Particularly, it details each study's purpose, methodological choices, and conceptualization of organisational performance or effectiveness.

2.2.THEMATIC ANALYSIS FINDINGS

The reviewed literature suggests that organizational performance in sport industry, particularly in football sector, goes beyond counting medals or participation rates as a dimension of an organizational success. In the case of football academies, the most effective programs prioritize a clear pathway to the professional team, stakeholder's satisfaction, governance structure, academy reputation and organizational image. Thus, the thematic analysis had identified a multidimensional characteristic of the organizational performance on the organizational research area (Braun & Clarke, 2006). In the other hand, the football academy effectiveness assumed that the efficiency of development pathway of football players to the first team by developing the talent identification process and practices. As such, the evolution of the talent should be shifted from subjective scouting to a multidisciplinary approach including technical, tactical, physiological and psychosocial factors.

Lastly, the strategic alignment and the Football Performance Support Model (FPSM) advance a key principal for sport organizations: effectiveness requires strategic alignment between three entities: support teams, club vision (youth development, brand identity...), and head coach's tactical approach (playing style, training...).

Table 8. Overview of included studies and presentation of findings

Author(s) and Year (First published)	Purpose of the study/ Central topic	Journal name & Country of study	Article type /Method of data collection	Definition & Dimensions of Organizational performance	Implications
Frisby, W. (1986)	Determine the nature of relationship between bureaucratic structure, goal attainment, and system resource models of effectiveness.	Canadian Journal of Applied Sport Sciences, Canada	Quantitative: Multiple methods: Documentary analysis, survey, and interviews.	World ranking (goal attainment), and operating budget (system resource). Complementary relationship between goal and systems models.	Demonstrates that goal and system models are complementary; effectiveness is closely tied to budget acquisition.
Chelladurai et al. (1987)	Identify and explain the dimensions of organizational performance and assess their relative importance to NSO administrators.	Canadian Journal of Sport Science, Canada	Quantitative : Survey	Input, throughput, and output for both elite and mass sport.	The effectiveness frameworks should integrate the cultural background as a variable aligned with the club vision and head coach tactics.
Papadimitriou & Taylor (2000)	Develop a measurement inventory for organizational performance and analyze differences in ratings among constituent groups.	Sport Management Review, Greece	Quantitative : Survey	Caliber of board, focus on athletes, internal processes, strategic planning, and sports science assistance.	The study demonstrates that a single stakeholder cannot offer a general idea of organizational performance. Also, the concept of organizational effectiveness has an approach that accounts for various stakeholders' perspectives.

<p>Bayle & Madella (2002)</p>	<p>Evaluate organizational performance across national sport organizations and analyze the taxonomy of performance profiles.</p>	<p>European Journal of Sport Science, France</p>	<p>Quantitative : Survey and expert's judgment</p>	<p>Institutional, internal and external social metrics, economic/financial indicators, promotional measures, and organizational variables.</p>	<p>The research highlights how organizational atmosphere, leadership, and professionalization in achieving high-performance outcomes in national sport organizations. Also, the study argues against reducing organizational performance to a single metric like medal. In this study, authors developed a detailed taxonomy of performance that classifies a range of profiles for national sport organizational.</p>
<p>Shilbury & Moore (2006)</p>	<p>Develop a psychometrically sound set of scales within the Competing Values Approach (CVA) to measure organizational effectiveness.</p>	<p>Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Quarterly, Australia</p>	<p>Quantitative: Multiple methods: semi-structured interviews (for tool design) and Survey.</p>	<p>8 cells of the CVA: Flexibility, Resources, Planning, Productivity, Information, Stability, Skilled Workforce, and Cohesive Workforce. Global evaluation based on associating qualitative and quantitative criteria. Satisfaction of multiple performance criteria based on four value sets.</p>	<p>The study reinforces that achieving organizational effectiveness in National Olympic Sporting Organizations (NSOs) is multi-dimensional and involves competing values. The authors introduced a useful framework to measure organizational effectiveness in sport organizations: Competing Values Approach (CVA).</p>
<p>Papadimitriou, D. (2007)</p>	<p>Select a set of metrics that accommodates that</p>	<p>International Journal of Public Sector</p>	<p>Quantitative : Survey</p>	<p>Board caliber, athlete interest, internal procedures, strategic planning, and scientific</p>	<p>Papadimitriou (2007) best methods for conceptualizing and measuring organizational effectiveness on no-profit</p>

	reflects stakeholder priorities	Management, Greece		assistance. Strategic focus in satisfying powerful stakeholder groups (constituency approach)	sport organizations. In these entities, organizational effectiveness is best conceptualized as the degree to which the organization meets the expectations of its key stakeholders.
Relvas et al. (2010)	Explore organizational structure and working practices concerning elite youth player development and senior team integration.	European Sport Management Quarterly, Portugal, England, Spain, Sweden	Qualitative : Semi-structured interviews	Roles/responsibility, youth-to-pro transitions, and club orientation. Player development efficiency and financial profit.	Elite football clubs must move from isolated academy structures to integrated organizational systems that promote clear communication, aligned objectives, and strong leadership. This integration is essential for successful player transitions, staff satisfaction, and long-term club performance.
Winand et al. (2011)	Analyze the link between combinations of key determinants and high performance using configurational analysis	Sport, Business and Management, Belgium	Mixed methods : Multiple methods: Qualitative interviews, annual reports, and quantitative measurement	Determinants (governance, brand, etc.) linked to strategic goals (customers, elite sport, sport for all). Ability to properly source and process human, financial, and physical resources to achieve	This study, using Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA), shows that high organizational performance in sport governing bodies is not achieved through a single factor, but through specific combinations of key determinants. Indeed, sport organizations should identify their own configuration profile rather than copying “best practices” from high-performing organizations.

<p>Winand et al. (2014)</p>	<p>Synthesize literature to provide a multidimensional unified model of NPSO</p>	<p>Managing Leisure, N/A (Literature review)</p>	<p>Mixed methods : Literature review and correlation analysis</p>	<p>Macro-dimensions: Input, Throughput, Output, and Feedback. Acquisition of necessary resources and their efficient use through organization processes to achieve targeted goals and stakeholder satisfaction</p>	<p>Understanding organizational performance in non-profit sport organizations has many aspects. A unified model that integrates different theoretical perspectives offers a more realistic way to manage, measure and improve performance than isolated or one-dimensional approaches. It also provides a stronger basis for demonstrating value to government funders, sponsors, and members. Such as, managers and boards can use the model for better strategic planning, priority setting, and diagnosis of organizational strengths/weaknesses.</p>
<p>Hamann & Schiemann (2021)</p>	<p>Specify the relationships between organizational performance and its dimensions using large-scale empirical analysis.</p>	<p>Journal of Business Research, USA</p>	<p>Quantitative : Secondary, objective archival data (firm-year observations)</p>	<p>Profitability, liquidity, growth, and stock market performance. Economic outcomes resulting from the interplay among an organization's attributes, actions, and environment.</p>	<p>Organizational performance is not unitary concept. It is best understood and managed as four interrelated dimensions (profitability, liquidity, growth, and stock market performance). Manager and boards should monitor and manage the four dimensions independently, recognizing potential trade-offs.</p>

<p>Mason et al. (2026)</p>	<p>Determine senior leader's perceptions of effective performance support teams in professional football</p>	<p>Managing Sport and Leisure, UK</p>	<p>Quantitative: Semi-structured interviews</p>	<p>Club vision, head coach approach, and the triad of practitioner knowledge. Organizational effectiveness through simultaneous strategic and tactical alignment.</p>	<p>This study explores how senior leaders (sporting directors, heads of performance and head coaches) in professional football perceive and structure effective performance support. It introduces the Football Performance Support Model (FPSM). Additionally, leaders can use the FPSM as a diagnostic and design tool to audit current structures, improve communication, and create better role clarity.</p>
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3. DISCUSSION

This section discusses the major findings that emerged from the scoping review through a conceptualization of organizational performance within the specific context of football training centers. In this perspective, organizational effectiveness is conceptualized here as a capability that professional football clubs and football youth academies can develop and maintain through consistent practices, stable structures, and continuous learning processes into their daily operations. The organizational effectiveness in football context has received only limited attention for researchers, while extensive research exists on talent identification and development, match performance, and coaching methodologies. Overall, the findings of this scoping study indicate that, although organizational effectiveness is evidently present in elite sport, particularly within professional football, there is very limited empirical research dedicated to this topic. Most studies included through this review were narrowly confined to talent identification and development in professional football.

The gap between performance outcomes and organizational practices

A key limitation in the literature is expanding the field through comparative international studies and stronger theoretical integration will represent bridge the gap between performance outcomes and the practices that generate more effective management practices in football organizations. Thus, it appears that findings from this scoping review highlight to provide for football stakeholders with evidence-based guidance to enhance organizational capabilities and long-term success toward building resilient systems capable to generate and maintain a sustainable effectiveness process in their decision. Similarly, the studies discussed the implications of various practices designed to evaluate organizational effectiveness in sport context as a complex industry. In the context of football youth academies, the analyses reveal that the youth academies requires a long-term to attain outcomes.

Organizational performance: from a unidimensional concept to a multidimensional framework

This scoping review synthesizes that by analyzing of more than 50 key sources reveals a significant conceptualization of organizational performance in elite football. It has moved from unidimensional success metrics, such as win-loss records to multidimensional frameworks that integrate strategic alignment, stakeholder satisfaction, and academic efficiency. In most cases,

organizational performance in professional football academies has been narrowly understood through singular measure, most commonly sporting success (league position, trophies won) or financial metrics (revenue, profitability...). However, a growing number of contemporary works recognize that true organizational performance in football comprises multiples interdependent dimensions.

The practical Gap in Football Academies

While many clubs have achieved structural uniformity due to governing body regulations (e.g, UEFA, FRMF), a significant “practical gap” remains. This gap is characterized by an absence of structured communication protocols and physical proximity connecting youth training centers and senior teams which often creates conflicting game cultures and hinders player progression.

Organizational paradoxes

A significant insight emerging from this scoping review is the central role of organizational paradoxes in shaping how football clubs and youth academies function and pursue effectiveness. In most studies reviewed indicate that sport organizations operate in a state of permanent tension, they must simultaneously manage contradictory yet interrelated demands that are often difficult to reconcile. Four persistent tensions shape their pursuit of effectiveness: (1) Short-term results versus long-term orientation by delivering immediate sporting outcomes such as winning matches or qualifying for competitions; (2) Sporting success versus financial sustainability by balancing competitive excellence with financial management; (3) Commercialization versus institutional values where football clubs must operate as profit-oriented businesses to attract sponsors and global audiences; (4) Autonomy versus external dependency by striving for operational independence while remaining heavily influenced by external stakeholders including governing bodies (FIFA, UEFA), owners, sponsors, and media.

CONCLUSION, LIMITATIONS, FUTURE DIRECTIONS AND EMERGENT AREAS OF RESEARCH

In conclusion, this scoping review maps the evolution of organizational effectiveness research in football training centers. The study demonstrates a clear paradigm by shifting from unidimensional measures to multidimensional frameworks. Today, performance is seen as a socially constructed concept that requires balancing between resources (inputs), training processes (throughputs), and the achievement of diverse goals (outputs) while ensuring stakeholder satisfaction (feedback).

This scoping review provides a comprehensive overview of organizational research on performance and effectiveness in football training centers, professional clubs, and youth academies. The findings reveal a fundamental problem in football organizations, which demonstrates the confusion between performance indicators (measures) and their determinants (predictors). However, several limitations must be acknowledged, first, the literature search was restricted to the elite sport setting, potentially omitting relevant studies from adjacent fields such as recreational sport, sport-for-all, grassroots football, and disciplines like psychology, sociology, and organizational theory. A second limitation is that the review did not assess the study quality, and is consistently recommended in scoping review literature (Arksey & O'Malley, 2005; Levac et al., 2010; Peters et al., 2020). The review still delivers a significant insight: elite football clubs and academies demonstrate strong of organizational effectiveness in practice, but a major gap continues to exist in understanding the mechanisms that generate it.

In some organizational settings, this scoping review identifies several promising directions for future research on organizational effectiveness in football. For instance, future studies should give particular attention to longitudinal and comparative international studies that explore how youth academies build and sustain organizational effectiveness across different cultural, economic, and regulatory contexts. Furthermore, the researchers should adopt longitudinal tracking that follows the entire development cycle, from academy entry (e.g., U12) to long-term professional attainment. Thus, sport organization need to include external stakeholder's perspective, in order to have a critical need to assess performance through the eyes of external constituencies, such as fans, the general public. Lastly, the digital and social performance should be integrated in the organizational process in building organizational legitimacy.

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